

Ethics and Accountability in the Development of Artificial Intelligence - Anton Pervukhin

I. Introduction

The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) brings up serious ethical concerns about how it will significantly change human industries, jobs, and everyday life in the future. As of March 2025, AI systems can now instantly process financial transactions, help doctors diagnose diseases, autonomously eliminate targets without human intervention in warfare, debug complex code, generate high quality images, and generate essays of 500 reasons why Pineapple belongs on Pizza in mere seconds. While these systems are becoming a big part of daily life and may promote growth in human industries, this exponential growth in Artificial Intelligence comes with major ethical concerns that need to be addressed. It may potentially make decisions without clear human oversight, invade privacy, and reinforce biases with possible serious consequences (Russell & Norvig). If we don't have proper safeguards, we will potentially see AI systems grow beyond our control in the foreseeable future. Many others share these concerns with organizations like UNESCO, who are working towards ensuring AI is used fairly and responsibly by establishing global guidelines for countries to follow.

The important ethical issues on the development of artificial intelligence that we must focus on are three main questions: How can we prevent AI systems from reinforcing bias? Who is held accountable when AI executes a decision that may cause harm? And finally, how do we balance the innovation of AI systems with regulation to ensure safety? This research paper will explore and answer these questions by examining the ethical concerns of artificial intelligence, its potential dark side and positive applications, and how humanity can develop artificial intelligence to promote integrity, transparency, and control in our new fast paced world. By understanding artificial intelligence at a nuanced level, we can create ethical guidelines for humanity to follow to ensure that AI helps people, but without safeguards, it could cause harm.

II. The Brief Evolution of AI and Ethical Concerns

Starting with the brief evolution of Artificial Intelligence, our progress in machine learning has significantly evolved from simple computing machines to advanced models that are capable of reinforcement learning and adaptation. Compared to early machine learning that could only follow strict instructions, AI systems in 2025 can now recognize patterns, automate complex tasks such as driving a motor vehicle, and processing massive datasets. However, due to a lack of human understanding and emotions, making decisions based on moral reasoning or thinking critically are not things AI today can do, despite our rapid advancements towards automation. In the same way that we humans can understand the context of an environment, possess self-awareness, or have intuition, AI does not because machine learning is built on statistical

probabilities and mathematical models rather than genuine cognition. Machine learning in a nutshell consists of processing inputs and generating outputs based on pre-existing data, making AI incapable of having personal beliefs or any kind of desires that a sentient human being would otherwise.

With the background of Artificial Intelligence in mind, we can see why bias is a major ethical concern with AI systems. Numerous AI models learn from pre-existing data that may contain existing human prejudices such as Sora, OpenAI's video generation tool which has been found to contain sexist biases, showing stereotypical job roles and physical appearances of generated content. The generation tool would depict Pilots, CEOs, and professors only as men while women are depicted as flight attendants and childcare workers. So in order to achieve equitable AI systems, we must eliminate algorithmic bias because biased data can result in discriminatory outcomes as emphasized by research from the Harvard Kennedy School.

Along with the potential for biased pre-existing data, a lack of accountability could be detrimental to AI systems. Who can we hold responsible when an AI system executes a decision that may cause harm such as misdiagnosing a patient or screwing up a large financial transaction? This question is often left unclear. It is difficult to assign responsibility in these important situations, whether to the machine learning engineers, the companies deploying the AI system, or the flawed AI system itself which is why Princeton University's Center for Information Technology Policy highlights the solution for clear guidelines to be set in place to hold generative AI accountable.

With AI technologies rapidly advancing, privacy is becoming a growing concern. Reports suggest that the Israeli military developed a powerful system capable of analyzing massive amounts of intercepted Palestinian communications, supposedly for security purposes. This raises pressing ethical questions about surveillance and personal rights. We have to consider that it can make errors and reinforce harmful biases, which may lead to wrongful targeting or unfair restrictions on those under military occupation and it raises serious human rights concerns. This begs the question of really to what extent can unchecked surveillance and large-scale data collection carried out by AI systems threaten individual privacy and freedoms?

III. Ethical risks and The Dark Side of AI

Moving on to the capable malicious uses of artificial intelligence systems, we are now seeing increasing cybersecurity attacks with the role of AI. Threats such as cyberattacks, phishing scams, and deepfake frauds are becoming harder to detect and more convincing for those who fall to them because AI systems are becoming increasingly powerful and automated for hackers.

As if having a shortage of cybersecurity professionals wasn't bad enough already, they are now facing serious challenges with AI-driven malware that can analyze security defenses and create solutions to bypass them all in real-time. Those seeking to commit financial fraud and spread misinformation will now take advantage of artificial intelligence to create deepfakes, which can manipulate audio and video, outputting with almost perfect accuracy. New deep fake technologies have led a tricked employee in 2019 to transfer \$243,000 into the bank account of a criminal because they used artificial intelligence to impersonate a CEO's voice (Forbes), demonstrating the growing concern for online safety as AI continues to evolve with each passing day.

Going back to the spread of information, it's now easier than ever to spread false information online through generative AI by the creation of fake news articles used to manipulate public opinion. We can see how misinformation may spread like wildfire through social media because those platforms use AI systems to prioritize engaging posts for people, rather than accuracy to keep users hooked on their site. A study from MIT proves my point because they found that fake news spreads six times faster than real news on Twitter due to the algorithm on the site promoting engagement (Dizikes, Peter). If we don't enforce guidelines that prevent political deepfakes, AI-generated articles, and fake images from influencing the general public on news and social media platforms, our trust in journalism and democracy will erode.

Along with the major ethical risks of artificial intelligence that I've already gone over, we must pay attention to the dehumanization of Art and Culture caused by generative AI in recent years. In 2025, new generative AI models released to the public such as OpenAI's GPT-4 and Google's MusicLM can generate songs and poems that resemble works made by a human, except that it has no genuine emotion or lived experience used to create them. If artists simply relied on generative AI to produce new works, it would be ultimately useless because making the art becomes an automated process instead of an expression of humanity, defeating the purpose of having a deeply personal form of creativity. Unfortunately, since AI is so convenient to use for generating new works, many artists and writers have been replaced in creative fields, making it harder for those with true talent to express their creativity to find a job that can support them.

Going beyond the job losses in creative fields, we will see the loss of cultural diversity in the arts due to AI-generated works. The incredible creative works we see today in music, literature, and visual art are all influenced by lived experience, historical context, and unique traditions, giving these works a touch of humanity that we all know of. Contrasted with generative AI models that produce homogenized and repetitive art styles through the analysis of vast datasets containing existing works and patterns (E-SPIN). Another issue we have to figure out with generative AI is intellectual property rights. When AI generates a painting of the Swiss mountains, a rap song about love, or a fictional book about a tree house, who is the actual owner of the work? This is a tough question to answer because many models are trained on copyrighted creative works

without the permission of creators, leading to legal battles over whether creative works generated by AI can violate copyright laws (Appel & Neelbauer). If we don't create clear legal guidelines on AI-generated works, we will be left fighting between the ethics of ownership and originality in works.

IV. Positive Applications and AI as a Force For Good

In part 3, I've highlighted ethical concerns regarding artificial intelligence, but we must recognize the potential for AI systems to innovate and enhance the lives of people globally. As I've mentioned before in part one of artificial intelligence having the capability to help doctors diagnose diseases, early disease detection is significantly improved with the use of AI systems. For example, the algorithms that are trained by examining medical images such as MRIs and mammograms can identify hidden patterns from the human eye such as early-stage cancers that are very difficult for human-trained radiologists to detect on their own (Jaber, Nadia). Recently, researchers at the University of Cambridge have developed an AI system that can analyze biopsy images with very high accuracy, leading to a much quicker diagnosis of coeliac disease and patient treatment which will greatly improve the speed of our current healthcare system. So in the future as AI systems improve the speed of diagnosis and patient treatment, we can see significant improvement in the outcomes of patients and survival rates for common heart diseases and cancers.

In the classroom, AI systems already have the potential to revolutionize education with very personalized learning catered for each student. Public school systems will be able to assess the individual strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles through adaptive learning systems of each student to tailor their education to promote their self-actualization. With each student having their own customized learning path according to their own unique needs, education systems globally may foster more well-educated students instead of teaching the same learning style to a classroom of 30 unique students. Additionally, AI-driven tutors could significantly improve individual student grades by analyzing their test scores and assigning exercises tailored to a student's weakest learned topics in a class (Toppo, Greg). Not only can integrating AI systems in the classroom promote self-actualization and improve individual grades, it will make educational environments much more effective and inclusive.

In the workplace, factories are already becoming much safer due to AI systems taking over the most dangerous jobs that used to put human workers in real danger of injury and even death in some cases. Instead of humans handling high-risk tasks, AI-powered machines now manage heavy lifting, risky processes, and operations in hazardous environments. Over at Tesla's Gigafactories, robotic arms do the welding and heavy assembly work, significantly reducing the

injuries caused by exhaustion or human error. Workers' lives can be saved in chemical plants where AI-driven sensors constantly monitor for gas leaks and hazardous conditions before they become deadly for human workers. By shifting the most dangerous work from people to machines, artificial intelligence is preventing fatal accidents and saving lives on the factory floor.

I'd like to now shift my perspective to the large-scale innovation of artificial intelligence systems after analyzing positive applications on an individual level. The environmental conservation and the monitoring of ecosystems have been greatly improved by AI systems in recent years. There are trained algorithms that use sensory data and satellite imagery to accurately track deforestation activities, wildlife movements, and the health of ecosystems such as coral reefs which are the most vulnerable habitats affected by climate change. The insights found by AI systems in these ecosystems allow conservationists to respond quicker to environmental threats and disasters and to come up with strategies for preservation. For example, following a 7.7 magnitude earthquake in Mandalay, Myanmar, structural and environmental damage was analyzed very quickly and accurately through the use of AI-powered analysis of satellite imagery by relief organizations. Due to the speed of the AI analysis, aid groups like the Red Cross were able to prioritize and direct their relief operations effectively to those who needed their help urgently.

In addition to AI analysis saving lives, AI systems can greatly enhance public safety and the management of emergencies. We already have algorithms that can be trained by vast datasets of past weather events and patterns to accurately forecast natural disasters such as floods and hurricanes in communities to allow for improved evacuation plans and the allocation of vital resources such as food and water. Along with AI systems improving the forecasting of natural disasters, they're transforming the emergency response training by building skills and resilience for emergency responders through interactive learning experiences. At George Mason University, researchers in the College of Engineering and Computing were developing AI-augmented games to stimulate complex emergency scenarios for emergency responders to improve their skills during an actual emergency. Even with the growing number of natural disasters occurring in communities worldwide due to climate change, AI technologies will make a significant impact in safeguarding communities and in mitigating the worst impacts.

V. True Intelligence and The Question of Sentience

Before we answer the three main questions back in the introduction, we need to address that AI isn't truly intelligent in the way that people often imagine in 2025. AI systems will never be able to think, understand, or truly feel emotion like a human being does even if it may have the capabilities of identifying patterns and processing vast amounts of data to make it seem like it.

Current AI systems simply follow programmed instructions without any self-awareness whatsoever, despite some people believing that artificial intelligence might eventually become conscious in years or perhaps even tomorrow based on “AI hype” news or videos online. However, chatbots can generate very human-like responses in cases of conversing with actual people, but you have to keep in mind that AI doesn’t “know” what it’s saying, it’s only predicting the next word based on past data (Public Citizen). Even if an output of a chatbot such as ChatGPT may seem highly empathetic and human-like, people still need to understand that it came from data analysis and probabilities rather than genuinely understanding what the user is exactly inputting. This will become harmful if people become reliant on AI chatbots as a therapist, best friend, or a romantic partner in their daily lives, which may consequently contribute to the increasing rates of social isolation and anxiety of frequent users.

Along with the growing AI technologies being integrated into our daily lives, human oversight will always be critical no matter how advanced artificial intelligence may become in the future in solving our problems. We could risk losing critical thinking and ethical judgment that only us humans have if we become too reliant on automated systems. AI is still very prone to making mistakes being trained on past data, leading to severe consequences in high-stake areas like healthcare or criminal justice if no clear human oversight is established. A recent report by the Harvard Kennedy School emphasizes that to ensure fairness and accountability in AI applications, human supervision is always necessary even if the outputs are highly accurate and may seem flawless. Instead of outright replacing human decision-making, artificial intelligence should be viewed as a helpful tool toward the advancement of human society and improving lives.

Moving on to the question of sentience, I’m referring to the ability to be self-aware which is being fully capable of experiencing thoughts and emotions. As I’ve discussed about the limitations of artificial intelligence so far, it lacks these qualities. Generative AI such as chatbots may mimic regular human conversation, but there is no real sense of experiencing consciousness or any kind of feelings. AI systems don’t have any form of personal or lived experience like a human does when processing inputs, meaning they cannot truly be considered sentient. Even if AI systems in the future may achieve or potentially surpass human-level intelligence, they will always remain fundamentally different from human beings and the nature of consciousness may be impossible to replicate through a machine only if breakthroughs would occur in neuroscience.

Continuing with limitations, machine learning algorithms won’t ever be able to think independently or creatively through the recognition of patterns and the ability to create accurate predictions. Artificial intelligence today has a very vast gap between human cognition that is capable of empathy, moral reasoning, and creativity. Researchers at Princeton University explain that despite its sophisticated and advanced algorithms, AI still lacks the depth of the human experience and understanding and only serves as a mere tool. As seen in human beings, true

sentience in artificial intelligence is highly unlikely to ever develop with the gap mentioned earlier. In the next few years, we may see AI systems significantly improve at data processing and generation, but they will never completely replicate the emotion and nuanced thought of a human being.

VI. Preventing Bias in AI Systems

To address the ethical concern of bias in AI systems, we need to prioritize effective technical solutions to promote fairness. One technical solution is using algorithmic audits to examine data that may contain biases before using the dataset to train a model. For example, IBM's AI Fairness 360 toolkit is widely used and accessible for developers who want to eliminate bias in machine learning models by testing data for discriminatory and imbalanced patterns in their datasets. Similar to IBM's toolkit, Google's What-If Tool explores the performance of a model and how changes in data may affect the outcomes of a model for users. These tools effectively mitigate biases, but efforts to create more diverse datasets have significantly reduced bias. Following the 2018 study by Joy Buolamwini from MIT Media Lab, facial recognition systems powered by AI have reduced their racial bias by incorporating a wider range of skin-tone data, improved by companies like IBM and Microsoft. Some developers are also using advanced methods like adversarial training and fairness constraints in loss functions that allow training models to spot and correct their own biases and ensure fair outputs. By synthesizing these technical solutions and improving our current technology, we can make sure that AI doesn't keep learning biased patterns from its data.

Along with the technical solutions I mentioned before, policy shifts are equally important in preventing bias in AI systems. We need to promote transparency and accountability by regulatory measures such as the European Union's AI Act for instance which requires "high-risk" AI systems to disclose where they sourced their data and methodologies (European Commission). At the same time, we need to improve how AI systems are built by including more multidisciplinary teams in the development process. Instead of only letting machine learning engineers build the entire model, ethicists, sociologists, and domain experts can improve models by co-designing them. A good example of this is Anthropic's "Constitutional AI" approach, involving diverse teams that help create guidelines that shape the behavior of an AI system. Not only can these diverse teams bring different perspectives, they can ensure the final product is more ethical and responsible. Beyond internal reforms, some experts say there should be citizen review boards, especially in policing and healthcare, where biased decisions executed by AI systems can seriously affect people's lives. Public boards could ensure that AI tools are being utilized to respect the law and that the people hold companies accountable. If we combine these

technical, regulatory, and cultural initiatives, equity would become a top priority from design to the deployment of AI systems.

The New York Times and MIT Technology Review have reported on how biased facial recognition systems powered by AI can have significant consequences on people, reinforcing the societal inequities that we see today. Even the American Civil Liberties Union pushes for greater transparency and accountability in the use of AI systems that contribute to discriminatory practices that we are about to go over. A real case of biased AI technologies in recent years comes from the usage of facial recognition systems by law enforcement. In 2019, a report by the National Institute of Standards and Technology confirmed that many facial recognition systems still had much higher error rates when identifying people of color compared to white people which can cause larger issues with identification. As a result of the report, there were several major cities including Boston and New York who either paused or redeveloped the usage of these systems when their potential bias could very well lead to wrongful arrests and false identifications of people who had to do nothing with a crime. Strong regulation and ensuring that AI benefits everyone are great solutions to making these systems fair. However, even the most advanced AI systems today can still cause discrimination if not carefully regulated which will set a precedent for future systems.

VII. Accountability Frameworks for AI

To address accountability in AI systems, it is essential that we must establish clear accountability frameworks in order to build public trust and prevent harm. There can be legal implications when an AI system makes a biased decision or executes a decision that results in death such as a car crash that begs the question of who's actually to blame for these actions? In Tesla's autopilot crashes for example, people may argue with "product liability" meaning that the AI system inside of the car was sold with a defect. However in other cases like Clearview AI, massive privacy violations can be committed with scraping billions of images from the internet without user permissions, pushing towards the idea that the company itself is responsible for the harm it causes known as "strict liability". Researchers at Stanford University in their 2023 AI Index Report stated that clarity is still a challenge for AI systems and it's difficult to assign blame when damages are caused.

So how can we hold AI systems accountable in the real world? One solution is a tool called Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) that makes an AI explain itself and its own processes. It can be highly effective because if an AI system would deny someone a loan, XAI can prove that the decision was because of a low credit score and not a biased decision such as their sex or ethnic background. To build trust and uphold accountability, AI systems can be trained to explain their processes, rather than simply being given permission to execute potentially harmful

decisions on a daily basis. We can ensure that a human will have the final say on critical decisions made by AI systems, such as in diagnosing diseases or making legal judgments in another critical framework known as "Human-in-the-Loop" (HITL) mandates. The implementation of these ideas can already be seen in 2025 with the European Union's AI Act stating that before action is taken, a medical diagnosis made by an AI system must first be reviewed and approved by certified doctors. But what if harm still occurs by AI systems? In these scenarios, we can create special funds such as a "Data Tax" on big AI companies such as OpenAI, Microsoft, Meta and others similar to how oil companies must pay into funds to cover environmental damage with oil spills in the ocean. Creating a special fund for companies in the forefront of AI innovation ensures that victims of AI mistakes will be protected and won't have to fight difficult legal battles to protect their rights.

Moving on to AI systems in warfare, we must establish strong accountability with autonomous weapons and drones used to eliminate human targets. These are weapons that could pick and kill targets all on their own without a human ever pulling the trigger, bringing up serious concerns over accountability. Discussions at the United Nations over Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS) have been very difficult to come to a consensus because nobody can agree on who is held responsible if an AI system executes an error and kills innocent civilians. Was it the software developer? The commander who deployed the weapon? The country? The AI system itself? It's a very serious question. Some countries like the United States may argue that there will always be human oversight involved, but some critics worry it may not be enough to prevent reckless actions. Many others hold the same beliefs as groups like the Human Rights Watch and the Campaign to Stop Killer Robots are pushing for a total international ban, arguing that autonomous weapons are a step too far and makes real accountability impossible.

VIII. Balancing Innovation and Regulation

While unregulated AI innovation risks harm to society, overly rigid rules can slow down progress for positive applications of AI systems and we must strike a balance between policies that encourage ethics without sacrificing development. One solution to create an adaptive policy for AI is regulatory sandboxes, allowing tech companies and new startups to test their systems to ensure safety before releasing their solutions to the mainstream. Several countries including the United Kingdom have been exploring with its own AI Sandbox, letting companies test new AI systems used in healthcare with less limits during testing, ensuring no harm will be caused to patients. Singapore has another approach of being risk-proportionate with different applications of AI, meaning that regulations may be much stricter in sectors that may have significant consequences if errors occur such as diagnosing diseases while being more lenient in the development of chatbots interacting with customer service. Combining these two sustainable

solutions will foster innovation of AI systems while providing strong protections in high-stakes applications.

Beyond just testing AI systems, we must encourage tech companies to build ethical designs with positive intentions. One solution offered is through Ethical-by-Design certifications to ensure that AI companies can prove that their systems meet high quality standards for fairness, transparency, and privacy, similar to how buildings may receive a LEED certification for meeting sustainable environmental guidelines. Tech companies may use this special certification as a unique value proposition for their AI and may possibly be eligible to receive a tax break for their efforts of producing ethical systems. Another creative solution is requiring tech companies to implement open-source audits to their systems before shipping out. This can be implemented because in the finance sector, we already have the SEC requiring financial audits for companies to uphold regulation. Similarly, as suggested by experts and seen with initiatives like Meta opening up its Llama 2 model's code, AI systems could be required to have their code and data checked by independent auditors to look for hidden biases or safety flaws. This would make AI companies more accountable and help build public trust around the fear of AI technology.

When it comes to implementing regulation, various countries globally have different ways of enforcement. The European Union with its groundbreaking AI Act is taking a pretty strict, risk-based approach towards the rise of these new systems. They've identified AI systems that are very high-risk and put strict regulation on them, and they've even outright banned some uses of AI they see as too dangerous, like government social scoring systems that rate citizens. The United States on the other hand has generally favored a more sector-specific approach, meaning that different agencies make rules for AI in their own areas. For example, the FDA is currently overseeing AI in healthcare and the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) is dealing with new self-driving cars introduced by EV companies such as Tesla. I think that the best way forward is implementing methods of the United States and the European Union with global bans for AI applications that everyone agrees are terrible such as using AI to create deep fake pornography, combined with more specific regulation that can be tailored towards industries and cultural values. With balancing regulation and innovation, we can effectively enforce rules that ban the most harmful uses of AI while giving sectors enough flexibility to determine their own limits on the usage of these systems.

IX: Conclusion & Call to Action

In conclusion, the ethical development of AI requires people from across the globe with different disciplines to work together to ensure that all AI systems are aligned with human values. This

development process will have significant hurdles but my paper has demonstrated that we already have so many solutions to make moral alignment a reality. We saw that preventing bias means more than just building better algorithms, but it requires using technical tools like IBM's Fairness 360 to audit data and policy changes like including diverse teams in the creation process. To uphold accountability, we can't let complexity be an excuse to let more AI systems take on more responsibility over human lives. By enforcing Explainable AI (XAI) and keeping a "human-in-the-loop" for critical decisions, we can ensure that a person or company is always responsible when things go wrong. Finally, we can balance innovation with regulation by using smart strategies like the UK's regulatory sandboxes for safe testing and Singapore's risk-based rules. Together, these strategies show that we can build AI that is fair, accountable, and safely regulated which will achieve a future where we can trust the technology that we create.

Two main things are needed to make this future a reality. Global cooperation must be encouraged first, expanding on the AI ethics work already done by organizations like UNESCO. This could involve creating a new institution, similar to CERN, specifically focused on AI safety and alignment. Second, the way we teach computer science and engineering in universities across the globe needs to be completely changed. Ethics courses, similar to Stanford's CS221: Artificial Intelligence: Principles and Techniques class, should be required for every student pursuing these degrees. This will help ensure the next generation of innovators builds AI systems for only positive applications with integrity.

Finally, this is a call to action for both politicians and tech leaders. Governments must be smart and practical because they should adapt quickly to implement regulation against the clear dangers we face today, like deep fakes and misinformation. At the same time, they must create expert groups to plan carefully about future risks such as artificial general intelligence (AGI) that may cause mass unemployment and massive changes to various sectors potentially in the future as of 2025. For the leaders of technology, the challenge is to rise above the simple optimization for profit and to focus on benefiting the world with these systems. AI is a powerful tool that should be used to solve big problems for humanity, not just to get more market share. With these goals in mind, We must build AI systems that are only aligned with human values to only be used in positive applications. We have a chance to create a future where AI technology can help everyone, but only if we work together and act now with a clear purpose to advance humanity.

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